

THE RISE OF RENT-TO-OWN MODELS: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

The growth in rent-to-ownership has become an emerging phenomenon in the United States as its total factors change the structural nature of homeownership for people who could be otherwise locked out from the formal channel of accessing homes through purchase. This paper seeks to discuss the main issues that emerged when first-time homebuyers entered the industry, which include the following: high home prices, high interest rates, low wages, and restrictive credit protocols, all of which have made homeownership a dream that has become virtually impossible to achieve. A rent-to-own arrangement is a hybrid between renting and owning, which includes quality and affordability, easy qualification or credit check, and saving on rent through a well-structured payment plan for acquiring the house. However, it also has some drawbacks, such as high rental costs, defaults, and fluctuations in the stock market. This article looks at the prospects of RTA plans to increase homeownership, significant participants in the industry, and possible ways for regulating and boosting consumer advocacy. Finally, it examines the prospects of rent-to-own models in the United States, the continued development and regulatory policies, and the education of the client base to foster sustainable future usage of these models.

Keywords; Rent-to-own, homeownership, real estate market, housing affordability, first-time buyers, mortgage lending, financial barriers, credit building, alternative ownership models, consumer protections

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INTRODUCTION

Owning a house has been a widely promoted death dream, mainly because of its association with financial security, self-sufficiency, and investment mode. Still, this dream dwelling has been out of reach for many people, especially first-time homeowners, recently because of rising house costs, declining wages, and difficulty meeting housing loan standards. These challenges are already altering the environment within which real estate is currently being conducted in the United States of America and precipitating a search for new business models such as the rent-to-own. This approach provides an alternative way to owning a home for people who might not fit the conventional home-buying model.

Rent-to-own models have increasingly looked like an option that may solve this problem, making homeownership even harder. These models give people who may be currently unable to attract a mortgage a chance to rent a home but at the same time build towards a home purchase. Another beauty of the rent-to-own system is how much the renters can put aside on the accounts each month, thus enhancing their financial standing and long run as occupants with a property or two, perhaps waiting to own a house or houses. Nevertheless, these models also have numerous associated dangers and difficulties that should be incorporated into their use.

This paper seeks to explore the current emerging trends in the housing sector to understand how rent-to-own options are emerging as solutions. This paper outlines first-time buyers' main hurdles to cross, examines the workings of the rent-to-own schemes, and identifies the leading industry stakeholders. Also, it offers actual-life success stories and assesses the potential dangers of this particular type of arrangement. Estimations of its possibilities for going forward are also analyzed to understand the new face of home ownership in the Americas, derived from the given models.

Rent-to-own models decided a chance to cater to the housing market's affordability and create new avenues to homeownership. However, acquiring these benefits has some disadvantages, and these have to be seen to be able to overcome them. Based on the analysis of the benefits and drawbacks of rent-to-own, this article attempts to reveal the potential impact of this concept on the real estate market. Whether it will become the lasting trend and actual source of new terms and continued business success depends on factors such as regulation changes and market environment shifts.

Ever since house prices began skyrocketing, a larger population of the American populace has started looking for other ways in which they can get their own houses. Thus, rent-to-own contractual options have become one of the most significant trends for those who cannot obtain mortgage financing. Such models should continue to be popular, given persisting economic conditions that challenge people to come up with large down payments or meet traditional loan criteria. It is, therefore, critical to fully grasp the movements and repercussions of rent to own as it is crucial for everyone planning on this new form of home buying.

Figure 1: Rent or own

I. CURRENT CHALLENGES FACING FIRST-TIME HOME BUYERS

Table 1: Challenges Facing First-Time Home Buyers in the U.S. Housing Marke

Challenge	Description	Impact on Homeownership
Soaring Home Prices	Home prices have risen significantly, with median prices reaching \$416,100 in 2023. Low inventory and high construction costs exacerbate the problem.	Makes it difficult for first-time buyers to afford homes, extending the timeline needed to save for a down payment.
High Interest Rates	Mortgage interest rates increased to around 7% in 2024, compared to 3% in 2020, leading to higher monthly payments.	Higher borrowing costs reduce affordability and deter potential buyers from entering the housing market.
Stagnant Wage Growth	Wage growth has lagged behind inflation, with a 4.6% increase in 2022 not keeping pace with the cost of living.	Reduces purchasing power, making it harder to save for a down payment and qualify for a mortgage.
Tight Lending Standards	Post-2008 crisis regulations have led to stricter mortgage requirements, such as higher credit scores and lower debt-to-income ratios.	Limits access to mortgage financing for those with subprime credit or high debt burdens.
Rising Rental Costs	Rent prices are at record highs, especially in major cities, making it difficult for renters to save for a down payment.	Forces many to prioritize rent payments over saving for homeownership.
Limited Housing Inventory	A shortage of available homes due to labor constraints, zoning laws, and high demand has driven prices up further.	Increases competition for available housing, pushing prices higher and limiting affordable options.

1. Soaring Home Prices

The lack of affordable homes for first-time home buyers is a cause that has been exacerbated by the soaring rates in the housing market in the United States (Kotkin et al., 2015). According to the National Association of Realtors, while the median home sales price achieved its record \$416,100 in 2023 against \$329,000 in 2020, this growth has been well above both wages and inflation rates. For instance, in areas such as San Francisco, New York, and Austin, the median home prices are relatively higher, thus making it hard for most people aspiring to own their first home in the country. The accumulation problem is also highly evident in these regions, as most homes are sold at significantly higher rates than the underlying working population can manage.

Low inventory has been an influencing factor that has been elicited by the high demand as well as the rising costs of construction. There are the regions where price increases have been relatively moderate, and there are those where price increases have been tremendously high, thus contributing to the unpopular issue of affordability. Consequently, most interested in buying homes end up being locked out, including the youth and other financially constrained persons. According to a survey by Zillow in 2023, almost half of the renters said they wanted to own a home, but the main challenge was that they could not afford to save for a deposit or that the house price was too high.

This is quite in contrast to what it was like in times of pomp when people could own homes with stable jobs and good credit scores—the average time it has taken first-time buyers to save for the 20 percent down payment on the median price of a new house stretched out to more than seven years as opposed to a little over five years in 1990. This extended timeline has the effect of discouraging many people from owning homes through conventional methods. The increasing affordability gap has forced people in America to shift to renting or other home ownership forms, such as rent-to-own.

The rise in home prices has concerned many beyond individual buyers and their ability or inability to purchase. It impacts the measure of economic opportunity, as housing often constitutes a significant share of first wealth accumulation in middle-class families. Those who are unable to buy are now missing out on a significant milestone in their financial future.

These reasons are stirring up the desire for rent-to-own models since this program may offer a path to ownership, even if the buyer is initially unable to make the standard purchase.

There is also a social cost, as low to moderate-income earners are at risk of being locked out again by rising home prices. Many first-time buyers are considering other options, including entering contracts that allow them to rent properties to own them because of the difficulties associated with rising home prices. Although such schemes seem promising, the various forces of the market still need to be addressed to make them a viable option for buyers (Nyati, 2018).

Figure 2: The Housing Shortage Is Hurting Almost Every Part of the Economy

2. High Interest Rates

The housing market has also faced a problem of rising mortgage interest rates due to an increase brought on by the Federal Reserve's attempt at controlling inflation (Garriga et al., 2019). The average mortgage rate increased to 7 % in 2024 compared to roughly 3% in 2020. This sharp rise in borrowing costs significantly affects the housing rate since higher rates entail higher monthly payments for the same loan. High rates significantly affect the ability to purchase and own a home for buyers and individuals who cannot refinance their homes.

For example, a \$ 400,00030-year fixed mortgage home could cost a buyer about \$2,661 monthly with a 7% interest rate. On a similar basis, if the rate of interest were at 3%, the payment would have been around \$1,686, which is approximately \$1000 more each month. This added cost negates homeownership for many first-time buyers, mainly when, in addition to other costs such as student loans and healthcare, others include the expenses incurred in homeownership. The collective costs prevent many from acquiring property, leading them to seek the best strategies.

He further observed that interest rate changes influence the market because high int. rates will generally result in low demand for houses. The need for more demand may help restrain price increases. However, the affordability problem remains a cog because of the decoupling of wages and the cost of home finance. The price of credit likewise persists in posing a challenge to would-be homeowners, even as there may be some stabilization of home prices. Thus, programs that facilitate property acquisition on relatively flexible terms, such as the rent-to-own novel solutions, are receiving more attention as potential routes to homeownership.

They outlined that interest rates have their influence not only at the micro level, influencing start house construction, construction activity, or the general real estate market, but also at the macro level (Davis & Haltiwanger, 2024). This and higher borrowing costs delaying new construction activities will only add to the supply-side constraints currently affecting limited supply markets. Regarding home buying, rent-to-own arrangements entice many prospective homeowners because they allow them to evade the short-term adverse effects of high interest rates while gradually moving into ownership of the house.

These interest rates target buyer groups, which are mainly made of first-timers in the market, especially young people. Many millennials and individuals in the Gen-Z cohort are already guilty of starting with high levels of student loan debt; it also puts a damper on their creditworthiness and ability to meet higher monthly mortgage payments.

RTA can serve This demographic well because while today's rates offer an opportunity to secure a home, this also puts the buyer under constant pressure to secure a mortgage, which can be intimidating to many buyers.

3. Stagnant Wage Growth:

Home prices have continued to rise, as have mortgage rates, but wage growth has not been able to move at the same rate. As the Bureau of Labor Statistics reported, wage increases in 2022 were approximately 4.6% and, in some cases, did not surpass the inflation rate, so real wages continued to decrease for many people. Because of the wage stagnation, it became harder and harder for people even to afford the necessities of life – let alone save money for a down payment for a home.

This is particularly true for millennials and Gen Z due to the decoupling of housing costs and wages in the United States. These groups generally have high student loan balances and are entering increasingly saturated job fields. Therefore, they can afford the preset 20% down payment, crucial to competitive mortgage rates. Low and slowly rising wages and high and rising house prices constitute a formidable threshold effect.

The problem is that wage stagnation doesn't only impact future savings but also the capacity to qualify for mortgages. Lenders often use debt-to-income ratios to decide on loan eligibility; in light of these, stagnant wages are a massive wall about such quotas. Hence, the more excellent population resorts to taking up rent-to-own house deals that will enable them to work towards attaining full tenure benefits while enhancing their financial capacity.

The problems of wage insufficient growth can be augmented by other financial burdens, including the increase of healthcare costs and consumer credit, which reduce available disposable income for housing savings. As for people who need help to afford to allocate large sums of money for payments on a new home, rent-to-own programs are much less problematic as they allow them to become homeowners, spreading the savings process for years. It is a good time for renters to start saving money, paying off debts, and working on their credit score to be eligible for a loan.

The problem also has macroeconomic effects because it contributes to the decline of consumers' purchasing power and the slowdown of the general economy (Agri et al., 2017). Governments and businesspersons may have to intervene in wage increase rates to help people buy homes and to help build a sound housing sector. Thus, such forms of ownership as rent-to-own are the only source of hope for those who face wage decline.

4. Tight Lending Standards:

After the problems of the 2008 financial crisis, mortgage lenders made new stringent rules to avoid another housing bubble (Walks, 2014). These changes failed to curb some widespread defaults and have also made it harder for ordinary potential homeowners to access mortgages. Banks now insist on higher credit scores, leaner debt-to-income ratios, and higher down payments—a no-no for first-timers in the property market.

A report by the Urban Institute, published in 2023, showed that four in ten aspiring homeowners who are renters have a below 640 FICO credit score, which is subprime in the lending industry. They are unlikely to access the lower interest rates on mortgages and can sometimes be declined credit in the first place. Such reality puts enormous pressure on many potential buyers, and often, they turn to options like rent-to-own because it is somehow more options-friendly.

Tight credit conditions have also led to more prolonged mortgage procedures and added documentation that needs to be submitted. It becomes even more frustrating for first-time buyers to locate them for obvious reasons, given the complicated system. Rent-to-own agreements help by offering lease agreements to clients where they have to take possession of a property with the raw intention of buying it in the future once they meet the required standards in the credit market.

The more common criteria for evaluating mortgage risk are likely insufficient to consider the new-age purchaser's ability to manage expenses, let alone the lifestyle they can afford. Lease and purchase agreements are suitable in that they have the flexibility to accommodate such differences in the financial needs of the buyers, unlike mortgages. As such, they afford a unique chance to obtain credit to homeowners who cannot get this from traditional mortgage channels.

Rent-to-own strategies also have drawbacks, including the likelihood of paying even more for rent and other penalties due to not buying the property in question (Tajani et al., 2020). Potential participants have to critically select their choices and understand the conditions of these agreements. However, rent-to-own is an essential link to homeownership for individuals who cannot cope with the present stringent credit requirements.

5. Rising Rental Costs:

Real estate. Rental prices have risen significantly in all fifty states, putting more pressure on the already stretched first-time homeowners (Samuel, 2024). Rental rates have never been higher in many of the country's largest cities, leaving renters struggling to put anything aside each month toward a down payment. The Zillow report, conducted in 2023, established that the average monthly rent for a one-bedroom city apartment in towns such as San Francisco and New York is over \$3,000. These high rental costs dent many of the renters' income, leaving them with very little to save.

It is getting worse as the necessity of rental units presses on the demand side, outcompeting the supply side and consequently increasing the rents. Population expansion, minimal construction of homes, and the leasing trend among young people seeking mobility causes can help explain this demand. They end up with a highly competitive housing rental market in which tenants are forced to bid for properties, and rent prices are increased. These factors defeat the purpose of saving money for the acquisition of houses.

Housing affordability is not unique to large cities but has become a national phenomenon affecting suburban and rural renters, primarily middle- and working-working-class (Walker & Bennett, 2015). This means that, for many, the cost of renting puts their homeownership on hold, pushing it further into the future; some even have to prioritize other financial responsibilities such as repaying student loans, credit card debts, and others. One exciting proposal for rent-to-own businesses is indirectly providing a solution to renters through a purchase system that enables renters to save incrementally while paying rent to overcome the high rent challenge.

Rent increases are also a result of specific elements of inflation and disruptions in supply chains that impact the cost of constructing buildings (Bai et al., 2024). With these factors pushing up rental costs, interested homeowners may prefer to rent to own homes because they are affairs that incorporate a clear and workable system to help them own the property even during turbulent markets. However, participants should understand the financial implications they are signing up for since rent-to-own agreements generally attract higher monthly charges than leasing contracts.

Government policymakers should attempt to reduce the strain on people due to increasing rent charges and encourage affordable housing, such as constructing more rental housing units. If these steps still need to be prepared, other models, such as rent-to-own, can provide excellent options for first-time homeowners. These programs give those stuck in high-cost rentals options for breaking out of the rental cycle.

6. Limited Housing Inventory:

Some of the problems have been a scarcity of homes that are available for purchase, which has accelerated the rates of inflation in housing prices in many markets in the United States. COVID-19 also intensified supply challenges that stemmed from labor constraints, supply chain disruptions, and increased costs for materials that slowed construction. The effect has, therefore, been the emergence of very keen competition on the housing market floor where demand tremendously outweighs the supply, thus causing a spike in house prices, leaving first-time users in a challenging situation.

The limited inventory problem is complicated in regions experiencing high demand for the units due to zoning laws, or there needs to be more land, or it is environmentally delicate (Kwon et al., 2024). We also note that in some locations, especially in developed nations, community rejection of fresh development projects has also contributed to the scarcity of affordable, durable housing. These factors have posed a significant challenge to the ability of builders to meet demands in those areas and, especially in urban and suburban markets. The limited availability of homes continues to drive up the prices, which makes owning a house increasingly an unattainable dream for many.

It is also a reality that the inventory crisis involves not only the housing units, especially those characterized as single-family homes, but also rental properties (Kaul et al., 2021). Stating that potential homeowners increasingly resort to renting because they cannot afford a home, Wolf says that the resultant demand has pushed up the price of rental housing. This creates a cycle whereby every time the cost of renting and buying escalates, a situation that locks many people into long-term tenancy.

Rent-to-own models come in handy for any would-be home buyer currently grappling with a limited stock. Such programs help renters obtain property during market saturation and give them the necessary stability and the chance to own a house or apartment. Also, rent-to-own arrangements allow the tenant to cap a future purchase price so that they are not exposed to higher rent prices during the lease period.

The permanent remedy for a problematic inventory population will demand a policy change and the development of other dwelling units. Could the bumper incentives encourage builders to construct cheaper housing? Could zoning regulations be relaxed to allow for affordable buildings to be built? Could policy support for modular houses or tiny houses boost the housing supply? In the meantime, rent-to-own business models offer hope to people who need help competing in a market with few homes for sale.

II. WHY THE RENT-TO-OWN MODEL WORKS

Table 2: Benefits of Rent-to-Own Models

Benefit	Description	Example/Case Study
Bridging the Gap to Homeownership	Allows renters to lease a home while building savings towards a down payment, making it easier to transition to ownership.	Rent-to-own helps people who struggle to save for a traditional down payment by allocating part of rent.
Time to Build Credit and Savings	Renters have the opportunity to improve their credit scores and accumulate savings over the lease period, making them better candidates for a mortgage.	Divvy Homes reports on-time rent payments to credit bureaus, potentially boosting renters' credit scores.
Locking in Purchase Price	The home purchase price is often locked in at the start of the lease, protecting renters from future price increases in a rising market.	Renters in areas with rising prices can secure a lower purchase price through rent-to-own agreements.
Test the Home and Neighborhood	Renters can experience the property and neighborhood before committing to a purchase, reducing the risk of buyer's remorse.	Rent-to-own agreements allow renters to assess if a home meets their needs over time before buying.

1. Bridging the Gap to Homeownership

Rent-to-own agreements are made to assist renters with finding an affordable way to own a house by offering them an offer to buy the house at the end of the lease period (Anderson, 2014). In a normal rent-to-own structure, the tenant pays part of the monthly rent towards an amount that can be used to pay the down payment later. This way, renters can save money by remaining in a house they wish to own. Because it provides a clear progression toward owning a home, it is especially suitable for people who are having difficulties saving for a down payment besides having to pay high rental fees.

This form of credit tenure has several attributes, the most important of which includes the structured saving plan inherent in the rent-to-own models, more so for those who cannot afford the down payments that come with conventional forms of credit tenures. According to Zillow’s survey conducted in 2023, nearly half of renters who wanted to own a house said insufficient savings was a hurdle. Through the systematic saving part of their rent payments, renters can save for the down payment without the pressure of saving on a personal basis.

Rent-to-own contracts give long-term rental buyers a chance to buy a home when they cannot afford a mortgage at the moment. Lease terms enable renters to enhance their employment status, save more money, and upgrade themselves to qualify for a loan to own a lease. It is a good model for integrating renting and buying to provide the most efficient solutions for long-term homeownership strategies.

Rent-to-own contracts are a good opportunity to buy a house to live in, but potential participants should study the conditions and realize how many of their payments go to the down payment (Guajardo, 2019). I believe people must put two things into practice well to benefit from this opportunity: planning and fiscal responsibility.

Figure 3: Rent To Own Home

2. Time to Build Credit and Savings:

One key benefit of rent-to-own deals is the long-term lease tenure that helps tenants rebuild their credit scores while saving money (Manns, 2024). This is particularly important for customers with poor initial credit or other problems that might hinder them from getting a normal mortgage. Throughout the lease term, renters have covenants that allow them to adjust their credit scores to ensure they obtain a good rate in the future.

Some of the benefits, especially to renters, include monthly payments to credit reports by the rent-to-own companies. In the words of the National Consumer Law Center, simple things such as paying rent on time have effectively boosted credit scores in the long run. This may enhance the credit status and provide better facilities, rates, and terms for the tenants when they want to own the property.

The lease period not only has the GOLD time to build up credit but also has a timeline of saving money for a down payment amount. Since part of the rent amount is put towards the one-time payment, renters are saving for their future homes and, at the same time, creating a savings Buffett. This slow build of equity and savings can be especially helpful for those who need help with standard saving schemes.

Rent-to-own models also come with the dual benefit of allowing tenants to improve their credit status and save for the home. In essence, by the time the lease term is over, many renters have built their financial capacity to accommodate the cost of a home and are also in a better position to have a better credit score than their neighbors and have saved for a bigger down payment,

3. Locking in Purchase Price:

Another advantage of renting to own a house is that the price of the house will be agreed upon from the onset of the rental agreement. This business can benefit renters, especially in real estate, where the prices are relatively low but are predicted to FLOAT higher shortly. To be specific, guaranteeing the price that rent applicants will pay at the beginning of the renting process gives them essential protection against the home prices' increase, which will be interesting, especially in districts with housing scarcity and, as a result, high prices.

It was further noted that prices between \$200,000 and \$250,000 were attainable by the end of Q3 2021 in some US markets homeownership largely and that home prices in some segment markets peaked by as much as 30% for 2020-2023. Some persons who engaged in a rent-to-own system based on their agreement during this period were able to secure lower prices than those directly involved in the purchase of homes and faced the complex difficulty of paying many times the cost of the homes. These aspects of price certainty may relieve the pressure for renters who otherwise cannot compete because of further relentless price hikes.

This system has pros and cons because, while getting a locked price on a property is effective if the market is appreciating, the market is always a gamble. This means that if the homes lose value during the lease period, the renters can, in fact, pay more than the price of the home at the time of purchase. Hence, renters should undertake considerable research on the market and the likelihood of the price rising any time that they agree to a rent-to-own situation.

Maalwormsvy also needs to know the conditions regarding other aspects of the locked-in purchase price, including different issues about reopening the contract or calculating it. Concerning such details, it reduces the risks likely to affect the success of the rent-to-own business), making it possible to enhance the dream of homeownership.

Figure 4: Rent-to-Own Homes: How the Process Works

4. Test the Home and Neighborhood:

The rent-to-own strategy is advantageous because it allows tenants to live in the home and experience the neighborhood before deciding to purchase (Hill, 2019). This way, a consumer can assess the property’s conditions and the community they want to live in, helping to avoid one of the common problems many homeowners face: buyer’s remorse. A survey conducted by Trulia in 2022 found that 60% of homebuyers regretted their purchase, often citing issues related to the location, size, or condition of the homes.

Exploring the property as a home for the specified lease period enables renters to gauge the property's suitability. They can also determine whether factors like proximity to stores, local traffic, or nearby schools play a significant role in long-term satisfaction. The opportunity to "sample" such aspects makes it easier to make an informed decision about completing the purchase.

Intervals of renting are also appropriate for assessing the quality of the home and deciding whether further repairs or improvements are necessary. This knowledge allows potential homeowners to make financial provisions to avoid unexpected expenses after the purchase. Another benefit of the rent-to-own plan is that lessees can negotiate terms for improvements or address contingencies before owning the property.

The possibility of renting the home before purchasing it can provide confidence and eliminate the risks associated with making a poor decision. For many, this opens up a chance where rent-to-own appears to be a safer proposition compared to a traditional home purchase, where this type of analysis may not always be feasible (Nyati, 2018).

Figure 5: Reasons Why Renting Could Be Better Than Buying

III. ORGANIZATIONS OFFERING RENT-TO-OWN SOLUTIONS

Table 3: Key Players in the Rent-to-Own Market

Company	Model Description	Unique Features
Divvy Homes	Requires a small down payment (1-2% of the purchase price) and allocates approximately 25% of monthly rent payments toward equity in the home.	Tech-driven platform with financial education resources and transparency in tracking savings.
Landis	Allows renters to select a home, which the company purchases on their behalf. The lease term ranges from 12-24 months, during which renters build savings and improve their credit.	Personalized financial coaching and flexible terms for non-traditional income sources.
Home Partners of America	Offers renters the option to purchase their leased home at any time during the lease term, with a transparent pricing structure.	Operates in over 80 metropolitan areas, providing a flexible timeline for purchasing the property.

1. Divvy Homes

Divvy Homes is a tech company that offers the opportunity for individuals with little or no credit who cannot secure a home loan to rent houses they end up owning (Mela, 2020). The company's model is based on a down payment, which ranges from 1-2% of the home's value; Maid outliers Mo, coupled with rent with a quarter of the rent amount going towards paying off the home's equity. This structure enables the renters to save small amounts towards a down payment. At the same time, they reside in the house they intend to purchase, and the program provides an avenue of homeownership for people with poor financial or credit standing.

The company has gained a lot of market in the United States, helping over 5000 families own homes by 2023. Financial literacy and adherence to a model of managing money are two of the spheres Divvy Homes focuses on by offering its customers relevant materials and special savings plans. The following resources support the tenant in getting a better credit score, learning how to handle money, and planning on getting a mortgage when the right time to buy a house comes. Housing finance technology can help structure the homeownership process better alongside better funding of the home buying process.

There is also a plan for how Divvy will ensure transparency at every level of rent-to-own (Nethercote, 2024). Another feature of the company's platform is that renters can see their equity score and track amounts saved toward the down payment. This may also mean that the focus shifts toward how renters can build ownership through strategic renting at this level of support, and disclosure is unlikely to exacerbate the problem.

2. Landis

Another industry giant in the rent-to-own industry is Landis, which primarily exists to help renters transition into homeownership by leasing homes with the hope of buying them (Frank, 2024). The company enables clients to select homes from the available list, and Landis purchases them for such clients. Tenants sign a lease to live in a house for 12 to 24 months, during which they pay their rent, rebuild their credit, and try to save for a deposit to buy the premises by the end of the lease term. This more flexible time frame allows those renting the property to make substantial progress financially.

In the year 2022, Landis was capable of raising over \$100 million to help expand its platform and improve services. Since then, it has engaged real estate agents across the country to have access to more renters and offer a smooth transition from renting to owning a home. Many clients looking for rent-to-own opportunities are shielded from the expert advice of industry professionals, and Landis expects to change that. A unique aspect of the company's business model is that renters get personalized financial advice that reflects their circumstances.

It is also important to note that Landis attaches flexibility to their rent-to-own agreement section, allowing any income and credit. However, since it is entirely interest-based, the approach suits renters with non-traditional employment or income volatility. Due to the bespoke advice and flexible conditions, the Landis organization beneficiaries the rent payment that enhances the financial recording while proposing a strategy for becoming an owner.

3. Home Partners of America

Because of this, Home Partners of America has designed a rent-to-own system that allows renters to buy the homes they occupy at any time throughout their lease period. The firm has outlets in over 80 metropolitan markets in the United States, with clear price tariffs that make rent-to-own quite easy and explicit terms for anyone wishing to engage in the business. An important aspect of this is the ability to purchase the house under lease at any time, and this gives the renters price control since they can buy the house when they are financially qualified to do so.

This suburban-based company has targeted and supported thousands of families across the United States to enable them to own homes through a friendly and flexible home-buying model. The company's program is based on separating the choice of the house and the movement toward ownership from the current financial realities, providing renters with options to select a property as rent and build their way up to the mortgage qualification. The fact that the purchase price is frozen at the start of the lease also gives this type of market segmentation a sense of certainty and security, especially if home prices are quickly soaring.

Regarding the customer, Home Partners of America focuses on the clarity of the contractual relations, which allows the renters to make the right decision (Lawton, 2015). Having a broader customer base means that the company can easily assist clients in diverse real estate markets, which makes rent-to-own homes relevant as a means of enabling people in many areas to acquire homes.

IV. REAL-LIFE STORY: FROM RENTER TO HOMEOWNER THROUGH RENT-TO-OWN

Case Study: [Gabby's Journey to Homeownership with Divvy Homes](#)

1. Gabby's Journey with Divvy Homes

Gabby Jacobs and her husband, Erin Bullock, lived in apartments in Bedford, Ohio, under conditions with many problems, such as no heating and a non-working stove. Many had regular employment and savings, but credit scores of around 600 excluded them from an affordable mortgage. When their real estate agent recommended Divvy Homes, they did not believe it; they heard many unhappy stories about 'rent-to-own' businesses. However, they opt for the opportunity after discovering how Divvy is free and follows a proper financial procedure.

The couple decided to live in a four-BR Cape Cod house, which Divvy bought for \$122,000, setting the couple's RTO price at \$136,000. According to it, 20% of their monthly rent payment was credited to equity; hence, they saved enough to buy the house. The choice was profitable due to its low monthly payments. Nevertheless, higher monthly payments were a problem, but the couple was willing to provide a safe environment for their children. That was when Gabby and Erin were willing to make it work for homeownership to build equity with each payment.

The most notable aspect of Divvy was the clear process applied to the Hi-Lo method since Gabby and Erin could monitor their progress to ownership through the firm. They also received access to Divvy's financial literacy tools, which taught them how to build credit scores and prepare for getting a mortgage. This support was helpful in eliminating the challenges that used to bar them from accessing standard financing.

V. CHALLENGES AND RISKS OF RENT-TO-OWN MODELS

Table 4: Challenges and Risks Associated with Rent-to-Own Models

Risk/Challenge	Description	Potential Impact
High Rent Payments	Rent-to-own agreements often have higher rent than traditional leases, as a portion is set aside for the future down payment.	Can strain renters' finances, especially in high-cost cities, limiting their ability to save for other expenses.
Risk of Default	Renters may forfeit any money paid toward the home if they cannot secure financing or keep up with payments by the end of the lease term.	Loss of investment and potential eviction from the property.
Varying Contract Terms	The terms can differ significantly, with some requiring the renter to purchase the home at the end of the lease and others including steep penalties for opting out.	Can create confusion and disadvantage renters who are not well-informed about the contract details.
Market Volatility	Locking in a purchase price can be a disadvantage if the housing market declines during the lease term, leaving the renter with negative equity.	Renters may end up paying more than the home's current value when it is time to purchase.

1. High Rent Payments

The major demerit of rent in the rent-to-own model is a scenario whereby one might have to pay higher rent than they would have just rented (Hu et al., 2022). The tenant is charged higher than average rent as part of the rent payments since some of the monthly amount goes towards the future down payment. This added cost could put high pressure on rent consumers, especially those taking Housing in cities like San Francisco, New York, or Miami, where Housing is very costly. In such cities, even the total of the rent and the saving portion may prove too expensive for many to handle on a monthly basis.

For instance, the median rent for a two-bedroom apartment in places like San Francisco is more than \$ 3,000 monthly. In contrast, including a rent-to-own premium may sound a little; it may significantly raise monthly payments. Even though the idea of building up the cumulative savings is beautiful, the added cost is well off the reach of some renters, especially those with tight budgets. This challenge can narrow down the affordability of rent-to-own for clients operating on a shoestring budget or those with an unreliable income.

The payments that should be spent on rent may hamper the ability to save for other issues, for instance, rainy day funds, paying back debts, and other expenses among renters (Adams & West, 2015). The latter agreement, however, involves more funds being paid each month than would probably be offered in a standard rental agreement – this may discourage some prospective renters from going for rent-to-own deals if they have better, cheaper options. Evaluating the general cost of a rent-to-own agreement will enable the assessment of the program's general suitability to the renter. Any interested candidates should conduct a cost-benefit analysis to determine whether the advantages of the operating lease outweigh the increased monthly costs. It's always important to discuss things like this with a financial advisor and see how it would affect their finances as renters.

2. Risk of Default:

There is also possible failure if one party fails to meet the agreement's terms and conditions of the rent-to-own agreement. If renters fail to make monthly payments or fail to source for the finances at the end of the lease period, they may miss out on owning a home. Additionally, they can lose any amount they contributed through higher rental charges or options fees, resulting in an impossible loss. Other rent-to-own contracts require renters to make very strict purchase commitments, which can cause them to lose their homes and money.

This risk is, however, further magnified by the fact that not all rent-to-own agreements are covered under the same laws as regular real estate sales. As a result, some of the contracts might be less favorable to the renter by having additional charges, restrictions, or conditions for early termination of the lease. In most cases, RTA arrangements necessitate more consideration than ordinary leasing because the obligations and exposure are normally higher.

People involved in the renters should exercise much caution when signing any rent-to-own contract and always ensure they thoroughly go through it (Floyd, 2024). Any legal or financial expert can assist with understanding if there are any pitfalls in the agreement or if they enter beneficial conditions. The rationale for wanting to learn the circumstances in which a renter may lose their investment includes not getting a mortgage by the lease term or paying rent on time.

Stone suggests that renters also have to evaluate their financial positions and factors likely to affect them in the future to avoid the risk of default. One way of ensuring that renters can meet the increased payments is to agree and set for the lease term a suitable payment plan that will enable them to cater for other expenses that are incidental in the process; another solution is to save more cash to cater for all costs as they arise during the lease term.

3. Varying Contract Terms:

Despite this, the terms of rent-to-own agreements depend on the company or the landlord providing the rent-to-own deal (Anderson, 2014). In this case, some contracts may allow the tenant to purchase from the developer in a phased manner, while others may require the tenant to take a lease and buy the property once and for all. However, some of these contracts might attract hefty fees for tenants who fail to opt out of the purchase of the home, meaning that they are locked in whether or not they can afford the home or whether they want to live in that property. This is because variability in the terms within the contracts put to the renters can present some confusion and raise risks to the renters.

Renters must be aware of the details of the rent-to-own agreement more so to them. Details include the period taken to purchase the home, any charges they are willing to incur, conditions under which they can cancel the agreement, and how the rent paid will be applied to the home purchase. Sometimes, an agreement also considers the renter to be in charge of the maintenance issues and the need for repairs, which can contribute to the general cost of the contract.

Because there is no uniform law addressing the rent-to-own industry, some agreements may have provisions clearly in favor of the seller or the landlord. This challenge requires special attention from the rent-seeking party to ensure that the terms of the contract are balanced and correspondingly suitable for the long run. One may consult a real estate attorney to learn the terms or avoid such strings attached.

To avoid unpleasant consequences, renters must conclude agreements that allow them more freedom and clearly indicate the circumstances that will enable the party to escape from the agreement without huge losses. To reduce these risks, the contract's provisions must be reasonable so that the business model of rent-to-ownership can become a viable option for those who rent an apartment.

Figure 6: Rent-to-Own Homes:

4. Market Volatility:

Another threat to renters amid market fluctuations is the price ceiling for purchasing homes under the rent-to-own arrangement (Fields & Vergerio, 2022). Getting a purchase price at the time the lease is signed can prove beneficial when the housing market is growing, but it becomes a disadvantage when it is shrinking. In case the market turns at some time during the agreement, the renters may be forced to purchase the house at far much higher prices than what the market holds at that time. This risk is mostly found in volatile price markets due to economic change or shifting regional demand.

Where house prices decline, tenants also risk a negative balance sheet where the cost of the dwelling is more than the property's value. This situation can precipitate an economic hardship wherein individuals who intended to switch homes within a short period would be forced to get a dwelling unit. Negative equity also reduces the number of choices available when refinancing and impacts long-term personal financial planning. The price of homes is also likely to change in a given market. Thus, renters should assess the chances of such changes before signing rent-to-own deals.

The probability of experiencing high fluctuation in the market is real (Bloom, 2014). To manage these risks, renters can take their time to study the market trends and approach real estate industry experts to forecast what the prices will look like at some point in the future. It is also possible to come across some free-rent term options in rent-to-own contracts that state that in case of a market crash, the renter has a right to make new negotiations regarding the purchase price for the property.

The prospect above of market fluctuation should form part of the key considerations that a potential tenant has when accessing rent-to-own tenancies. With this understanding of the risks and planning about possible changes in home values, the renters can make good decisions that will help them avoid challenges and potential failures when purchasing.

Figure 7: Economics Principle: Price Controls on Rental Market Essay

VI. OPPORTUNITIES FOR POLICYMAKERS AND INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDERS

Table 5: Regulatory and Policy Opportunities for Rent-to-Own Programs

Opportunity	Description	Examples of Potential Actions
Enhancing Consumer Protections	Establishing standards for contract transparency, tenant rights, and fair rent-to-own practices to avoid exploitation.	Requiring the disclosure of fees, penalties, and conditions for opting out; introducing mandatory inspections and reporting on property conditions.
Standardizing Contract Terms	Implementing guidelines for uniform rent-to-own contracts to reduce variability and ensure fair terms for all renters.	Setting industry-wide standards for payment structures, equity allocations, and tenant obligations.
Encouraging Affordable Programs	Providing incentives such as tax credits or grants for companies that offer affordable, transparent rent-to-own programs to underserved communities.	Government partnerships with private companies to expand rent-to-own programs in areas with high housing costs.
Promoting Consumer Education	Launching educational campaigns to inform potential renters about rent-to-own agreements, risks, and financial planning strategies.	Creating resources like financial counseling services and legal aid for renters entering rent-to-own agreements.

1. Enhancing Consumer Protections

The rent-to-own models offer substantial prospects for delivering homeownership opportunities, but with these chances comes the challenge of ensuring that consumers are protected against predatory practices (Rosen et al., 2017). These contracts may include additional fees, unfair terms, or strict conditions that disadvantage clients, particularly low-income renters. By promoting best practices in rent-to-own agreements, lawmakers could create fair and feasible options in the housing market for first-time homeowners. This could involve establishing guidelines to standardize contracts across the industry, explicitly defining tenants' rights, or proposing rules that mandate clear language for terms disclosure to safeguard consumers.

Regulatory authorities can also take an active role by implementing rules to standardize various contract types used by rent-to-own companies. Standardization helps reduce tenants' exposure to complex and unfavorable agreements. Legislation that clarifies fee structures in rent-to-own contracts would be helpful for renters. Additionally, rules requiring landlords or property owners to disclose the condition of the premises and any hidden issues can help avoid excessive charges imposed on tenants.

To encourage fair rent-to-own agreements, incentives should be provided for offering fair programs to consumers. For example, tax credits or grants could be given to industry participants who comply with best practices or to developers who provide affordable housing solutions for those excluded from traditional housing markets. These incentives would motivate companies to prioritize tenants' interests and foster competition. Collaborations between government agencies and private organizations could further expand rent-to-own opportunities, particularly for those for whom conventional homeownership remains out of reach.

Consumer education is also essential in implementing rent-to-own techniques in the housing market. Potential tenants need to understand how these agreements work and anticipate future costs. Authorities could launch educational campaigns to inform renters of their rights regarding rent-to-own agreements, the potential risks, and ways to improve their credit scores and save money. Offering legal assistance, such as advice on contracts and financial consultation, would further support tenants.

Rent-to-own transactions could be designed to shield tenants from market risks (Stern, 2024). For instance, including terms that adjust prices in line with market conditions or allowing tenants to renegotiate lease terms if home values drop significantly would enhance security. Policies that support flexible terms ensure that rent-to-own remains a viable option, regardless of changing market conditions.

Legalizing rent-to-own agreements and providing legally binding provisions could help protect tenants from exploitation. This would require enacting standard state or federal laws outlining the legal relationships, protective measures, and conflict resolution processes, thus enabling tenants to better understand their obligations and rights (Gill, 2018).

Figure 8: SME finance forum

VII. THE FUTURE OF RENT-TO-OWN IN THE U.S. REAL ESTATE MARKET

1. Increasing Prominence in the Market

Rent-to-own plans are expected to grow due to continued problems with housing prices and affordability across the country (Japaridze & Sayour, 2024). Given the prevailing high property costs, high interest rates, and stringent credit policies, the conventional housing accumulation process remains a challenge. Flexibility applying will create an additional option for millions of renters in terms of how they can become homeowners, as rent-to-own continues to be viewed as one of the most realistic rental models. Thus, for these programs to attract increasing popularity, the real estate market may record a diversification of homeownership programs.

Rent-to-own contractual schemes will only be realized throughout the economy with the concerted efforts of all the real estate companies, policymakers, and financial institutions (Cassourret & Salenson, 2024). The partnership will be crucial in helping guarantee that rent-to-own deals will not be an exploitative, spike-rent trap and signifying genuine opportunities for people seeking homeownership. It will entail drawing rules of the game that would guard consumer interests while enabling the companies to fashion out efficiencies and develop sustainable models to suit different markets.

Mature systems in technology ownership and effective data analysis may also interfere with the future of the rent-to-own market. It will also be easier for potential tenants to learn about rent-to-own opportunities and the terms in any contracts signed and even monitor their progress in owning the house. In other words, enabled by technological advances, companies should be more capable of delivering more targeted offers that would fit the financial profile of renters and better prepare them for home buying. Purchasing with digital as rent-to-own could be the developing component of the housing market.

Several factors outside rent-to-own's immediate ambit may also define its prospects, including changes in economic conditions and housing... For example, mass policies such as interventions designed to enhance the construction of affordable homes or financing down payments may affect requests for RTO contracts.

If housing affordability trends deteriorate, rent-to-own programs may become the only relevant lever for increasing homeownership opportunities (Derkowski, 2024). On the other hand, if housing programs achieve their affordability goal, the requirement for other ownership structures should decrease.

Secondly, socioeconomic factors like the emergence of relativities with millennials and part of the generation Z in the housing market, for example, may act as causative agents for demand for flexibilities of homeownership like rent to own. Generations Y and Z have specific financial burdens in front of them, particularly students' credits and high rent prices; thus, purchasing a house is challenging. West and others point out that 'traditional' models of renting-to-own are well suited to the financial abilities of young people in terms of credit scores and saving for a down payment.

The prospects for rent-to-own in the American real estate segment will depend only on the industry's capacity to adjust to the emerging trends in the market and customers' requirements. Education for the consumers and continual improvements of these models, as well as political support in the form of legislation and complementary measures, will remain key to the broad applicability of these models as viable routes to sustainable homeownership. Therefore, if rent-to-own has been implemented, it becomes a permanent and important figure in the pictured housing market.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Rent-to-own has become more popular, highlighting how the proper homeownership deficiency is forcing more people to seek other forms of homeownership in the real estate market. Home prices are out of reach, mortgage rates are high, wages remain low, and creditworthy standards make buying a first home tough. Those with credit difficulties, insufficient savings, or other barriers that make it challenging to pay rent and purchase a home outright have a more structured way of overcoming these barriers through rent-to-own programs. The models are attractive to many because of the ability to freeze the price of a home, to 'try out' a community first, and to build equity with any rents paid towards a property.

Even though rent-to-own offers various opportunities to people aspiring to be homeowners, there are inherent dangers that go with it. Rent payments, the possibility of receiving no fees from the tenant or leasing company, and frequent fluctuations in the stock market make such agreements quite difficult financially for certain companies. Thirdly, different tenants may face unfair contract terms due to the absence of uniformity in the terms by the players in the industry. Therefore, prospective participants should research, consult professionals, and conform to all these requirements before entering into any rent-to-own agreement.

Rent-to-own can go a long way toward solving housing affordability problems and expanding homeownership opportunities, but the prospects will hinge on improvement and more potent regulatory policies. That is why policies regulating relations between platform and gig workers and consumers, determining fair rules of engagement, and exercising consumer protection can significantly influence the development of those models. However, the respondents believe that the industry's stakeholders directed enough attention to transparency and flexibility to make rent-to-own a sustainable concept.

Consumer education will also be instrumental in guaranteeing that renters can make the right decisions. This paper provides insight into the complexities of entering into a rent-to-own contract and the benefits and drawbacks of doing so. Thus, public and private initiatives offering resources, legal assistance, and financial advice will enable renters to appropriately embrace the status of homeownership.

These programs could revolutionize the national real estate market by providing a viable means by which the indigent could own houses, even as the housing affordability problem persists largely unabated. It will, therefore, depend on their capability not only to deal with existing problems on their way but also to master constantly changing conditions in the market and consumers' needs. When the main actors involved continue cooperating with renters, RE companies, and policymakers, rent-to-own applications might develop into a useful and viable instrument to help close the gap for first-time buyers.

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The Rise of Rent-To-Own Models: Opportunities and Challenges

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